

and intensities are the main hydrological constraints to rice productivity.

Cultivating mixtures of deepwater rice (DWR) is a prevalent practice in chaur. The varieties used have almost identical morphological characters and are highly adapted to sowing and transplanting conditions in the area. We studied the submergence tolerance of DWR varieties Darmi and Jagar under different hydrological conditions.

Five samples of 100 panicles each were collected randomly from deepwater rice-fields (200 cm maximum water depth) cropped with mixtures of Darmi and Jagar during 1990 kharif in chaur. The area was stratified into 50-100, 100-150, and 150-200 cm water depths. Based on kernel color and panicle characteristics, samples from each water regime were classified into three—Darmi, Jagar, and “others.”

Pregerminated seeds of Darmi and Jagar were sown 5 cm apart in five trays filled with soil on 12 Jun 1991. The trays with 14-d-old seedlings were completely submerged in a pond for 7 d with 30 cm of water above the tip of the seedling. On the 10th day of the recovery period, survival count and phenotypic scoring for submergence tolerance were done. The IRR standard scoring system was used; a low score indicates good tolerance.

Table 1. Number of panicles of Darmi, Jagar, and others per sample of 100 panicles, collected from three water depths. Vaishali, Bihar, India.

Sample	Water regimes								
	50-100 cm			100-150 cm			150-200 cm		
	Jagar	Darmi	Others	Jagar	Darmi	Others	Jagar	Darmi	Others
1	52	45	3	34	56	10	21	77	2
2	51	36	13	41	51	8	33	61	6
3	40	50	10	28	63	9	48	50	2
4	49	35	16	40	54	6	26	66	8
5	56	40	4	30	59	11	43	54	3
Total	248	206	46	173	283	44	181	307	21
Av	49.6	41.2	9.2	34.6	56.6	8.8	36.2	61.4	4.2

Table 2. Submergence tolerance scores of Darmi and Jagar. Bihar, India.

Variety	Tray 1	Tray 2	Tray 3	Tray 4	Tray 5	Av
Darmi	7	6	8	6	7	6.8
Jagar	8	9	9	9	8	8.6

Among samples collected from the 50-100 cm water regime, Jagar had more panicles (49.6%) than Darmi (41.2%), suggesting that Jagar was the better adapted cultivar with a greater number of effective tillers.

Among samples obtained from the lower niches of the chaur, Darmi had higher panicle number (56.6 and 61.4%) in the 100-1.50 and 150-200 cm water regimes compared with Jagar, which had 34.5 and 36.2%, respectively (Table 1). This indi-

cates that Darmi was better adapted to deep water than was Jagar.

Darmi had better submergence tolerance (av 6.8) than Jagar (av 8.6) (Table 2). This suggests that Darmi possesses genes that make it suitable for deepwater areas.

Developing DWR varietal mixtures with different levels of submergence tolerance but similar agronomic characters could be one way of minimizing hydrological constraints to growing rice in rainfed low-lying areas. ■

Effect of transplanting times on hybrid rice in Haryana, India

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We evaluated the performance of newly developed hybrids in India with respect to staggered planting. The field study involved four transplanting dates (15 Jun, 25 Jun, 5 Jul, and 25 Jul) and four genotypes (hybrids ORI 161, PMS2A/IR31802, and PMS01A/PR106 and check variety HKR126) and was conducted during the 1993-94 wet seasons at RRS, Kaul. Soil was clay loam, with pH 8.2, low available N, but high available P and K.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications; planting dates were main plots and varieties were

subplots. Plant spacing was 20 × 15 cm. The crop was fertilized with 150 kg N, 26.4 kg P, and 5.75 kg Zn ha⁻¹, with N applied in three equal splits: at transplanting, active tillering, and panicle initiation. Thirty-day-

old seedlings were transplanted in all dates except in the 25 Jul 1993 planting, where 40-d-old seedlings were used.

Highest grain yields were obtained when the genotypes were transplanted on 25 Jun

Effect of transplanting time and genotype on grain yield and harvest index. Kaul, India. 1993-94.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			Harvest index		Productivity (kg d ⁻¹)		Spikelet sterility (%)	
	1993	1994	Mean	1993	1994	1993	1994	1993	1994
<i>Time of transplanting</i>									
15 Jun	7.2	6.8	7.0	0.51	0.50	46.5	51.0	26.2	27.6
25 Jun	7.9	7.5	7.7	0.54	0.53	51.2	57.1	20.4	23.4
5 Jul	7.6	7.2	7.4	0.53	0.52	50.9	54.6	22.1	25.4
25 Jul	5.5	4.2	4.9	0.46	0.41	41.9	32.1	28.8	37.9
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.3	-	0.01	0.02	-	-	2.1	1.8
<i>Genotypes</i>									
ORI 161	7.8	7.4	7.6	0.54	0.52	52.9	56.5	19.2	24.4
PMS2 A/IR31802	7.3	6.6	7.0	0.52	0.49	49.1	49.8	25.3	29.7
PMS10 A/PR106	6.3	5.8	6.1	0.48	0.45	42.4	43.7	30.1	33.9
HKR106	6.9	6.1	6.5	0.50	0.49	47.3	46.4	23.5	27.6
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	-	0.01	0.01	-	-	2.0	2.0

(7.7 t ha⁻¹) and on 5 Jul (7.4 t ha⁻¹) in both years (see table). A drastic yield reduction was observed in the 25 Jul planting, but the rate of decrease was slower in 1993 than in 1994. This may be due to the use of aged (40 d) seedlings in 1993. There was 10.1, 4.1, and 57.1% increase in grain yield in the 25 Jun planting over that of 15 Jun, 5 Jul, and 25 July, respectively.

Harvest index and productivity (kg d⁻¹) were highest in the 25 Jun planting, followed by the 5 Jul and 15 Jun plantings.

Lowest values of harvest index and productivity were registered with the 15 Jun planting. Spikelet sterility was lower in 1993. It was similarly lower for 25 Jun and 5 Jul than for 15 Jun and 25 Jul. Percentage sterility was relatively higher for the late planting dates in 1994.

Among genotypes, ORI 161 (PHB71) produced the highest grain yield (7.6 t ha⁻¹). Hybrids ORI 161 and PMS2 A/IR31802 were found significantly superior to

HKR126 (6.5 t ha⁻¹). Productivity and harvest index were highest in ORI 161, followed by PMS2 A/IR3 1802 and HKR126. Spikelet sterility was minimum in ORI 161, followed by HKR126.

Planting hybrid ORI 161 resulted in a 17% increase in grain yield over the best available pureline genotypes. In northwestern India, the best time to transplant hybrid rice is between 25 Jun and 5 Jul. ■

Effect of solar radiation and temperature on rice yields in different planting dates

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Solar radiation and temperature are important climatic factors affecting rice yields under irrigated conditions. In an experiment to define optimum planting dates for the newly released high-yielding variety Morelos A92 and breeding line CAEZ401, the effect of these climatic factors on grain yield was assessed through regression techniques.

Soil is a Vertisol with pH 7.6, 3% organic matter, 0.31% total N, and 22 ppm Olsen P. Five planting dates with

3-wk intervals were evaluated, the first in 29 Apr and the last in 22 Jul 1993.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design at the experimental station of Zacatepec, Morelos with four replications, with planting dates in the main plot and genotypes in the subplots. Forty-five-day-old seedlings were planted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 4- × 4-cm plots. Water management consisted of periodical irrigation. Basal fertilization with 90 kg N ha⁻¹, 40 kg P ha⁻¹, and 40 kg K ha⁻¹ was applied 25 d after transplanting (DAT); additionally, 45 kg N ha⁻¹ each were applied at panicle initiation and at booting stage. Grain yield in a 9-m² area was measured and adjusted to 14% moisture on a wet basis.

Regression analysis with grain yield as the dependent variable and global radiation

(GR, estimated after sunshine hours) and minimum mean temperature (MMT) as independent variables were performed in three periods: from 20 d before flowering up to flowering (f-20), from flowering to 20 d after flowering (f+20), and from 20 d before to 20 d after flowering (f-20 to f+20).

Growth duration was shortened in the last planting dates because of photoperiod sensitivity of the two genotypes (see table). In the first planting date, Morelos A92 and CAEZ401 were harvested 137 and 125 DAT, respectively, whereas in the last planting date, Morelos A92 and CAEZ401 were harvested 120 DAT. Grain yield declined in Morelos A92 as planting was delayed (see figure), but in CAEZ401, decline was significant only for the late planting date.

Regression equations and parameters to assess the fitness of different models in the three periods. Zacatepec, Morelos, Mexico, 1993.

Model	Equation	R ²	(%) ^a	MSE ^b
<i>f-20^c</i>				
1	Yield ^d = 10328 - 4.6 (GR) ^e	0.16	25.9	2909314
2	Yield = 437393 - 49234 (MMT) ^e + 1410 (MMT ²)	0.07	78.1	3670335
3	Yield = 10599 - 93 (GR/MMT)	0.19	20.2	2776786
4	Yield = 916660 + 980 (GR) - 78858 (MMT) + 1496 (MMT ²) - 16751 (GR/MMT)	0.85	2.6	813472
<i>f + 20</i>				
1	Yield = 20 (GR) - 2411	0.20	19.9	2768937
2	Yield = 144952 - 17855 (MMT) + 571 (MMT ²)	0.81	0.3	758453
3	Yield = 12114 - 137 (GR/MMT)	0.02	67.4	3365802
4	Yield = 163592 + 37 (GR) - 18847 (MMT) + 568 (MMT ²) - 652 (GR/MMT)	0.81	4.9	1060182
<i>f - 20 to + 20</i>				
1	Yield = 28 (GR) - 6705	0.25	14.4	2595018
2	Yield = 47782 (MMT) - 1277 (MMT ²) - 437848	0.34	23.2	2594505
3	Yield = 305 (GR/MMT) - 796	0.09	40.2	3138594
4	Yield = 454149 + 367 (GR) - 44589 (MMT) - 1051 (MMT ²) - 6035 (GR/MMT)	0.49	40.9	2799678

^aObserved level of significance. ^bMean square error. ^cf - 20 = from 20 d before flowering up to flowering, f + 20 = from flowering to 20 d after flowering, f - 20 to + 20 = from 20 d before to 20 d after flowering. ^dkg ha⁻¹. ^eGR = global radiation. MMT = mean minimum temperature.